

Working in uncertainty: Organizational behavior of contingent college teachers in the Philippines

Eva Joy Canto Palma¹, George R. West²

¹Department of General Education, Faculty of College of Education, Northern Iloilo State University Barotac Viejo Campus, Iloilo, Philippines

²Graduate School Department, Faculty of Graduate School Program, Central Philippine University, Iloilo, Philippines

Article Info

Article history:

Received Aug 24, 2022

Revised Aug 18, 2023

Accepted Sep 8, 2023

Keywords:

Contingent teachers

Organizational citizenship behavior

Organizational commitment

Perceived organizational support

Philippine state universities

ABSTRACT

Several researchers have previously written about factors that contribute to the organizational commitment of employees. However, there are only few empirical studies on the impact of organizational commitment on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), especially among non-permanent employees and how these behaviors have been impacted by perceived organizational support (POS). This study investigated the contextual relationships of organizational commitment and OCB, along with the mediation effect of POS on those relationships in the context of contingent teachers in Philippine state universities and colleges. A survey was conducted in selected state universities and colleges in the Philippines with contingent teachers for academic year 2019-2020 as respondents. Findings of the study showed that the targeted population generally rate their OCB higher than their organizational commitment or any of the subcategories thereof. They also rated OCB higher than the perceived support that they receive from their given organizations. Results also found that POS, although correlating with OCB, did not mediate any of associated relationships. The results indicate that contingent faculty members develop and maintain commitment to their organizations from sources other than the perceived support that they receive from their organizations.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Eva Joy Canto Palma

Department of General Education, Faculty of College of Education, Northern Iloilo State University

Barotac Viejo Campus

Su Puerto Princesa, Barotac Viejo, Iloilo, Philippines

Email: yojave_19@yahoo.com.ph

1. INTRODUCTION

The employment of contingent teachers in higher education institution is prevalent due to new staffing patterns in academia [1]. The percentage of fulltime, non-tenure track faculty has doubled from 18.6% to 37.6% from 1975 to 2007 and it has tripled during the past three decades as nearly 60% of new full-time faculty appointments are now under temporary contracts [2]. Contingent faculty, also known as adjuncts, or non-tenure track faculty, represent two thirds of all faculty members in higher education in the United States [1]. Clay [3] confirmed this, stating that over 70% of the then current faculty workforce consisted of contingent workers. This observed changes in employment in the academe mirror larger trends in the United States and even in the global workforce [4]. In turn, researchers have assessed several of the underlying factors associated with the employment of these contingent workers.

The phenomena previously identified, concerning contingent workers in academia have primarily included: i) Causes of the increased employment percentages; ii) Physical concerns and outcomes, including

comparisons with tenure track faculty members; and iii) Associated organizational behavior dynamics. Although researchers have supported the administrative burden position, some administrators have pushed back, indicating that full-time faculty members, rather than administrators, receive most of the acquired institutional resources. Regardless of the causes, however, researchers have also identified associated challenges and results among contingent faculty members. These have included under-utilization of talent, low pay, low levels of support, low status, low self-efficacy, scheduling challenges, and questionable results in overall student success, especially when compared to similar challenges and results found among their full-time, tenure track colleagues [5]. Furthermore, researchers have also found and documented that generally, challenges and results like these necessarily impact the organizational behavior dynamics of the people who live these experience [6]. These phenomena do not represent concerns unique to academia in the United States only. Employment of non-permanent workers also represents a common practice in both private and public sectors in the Philippines.

In the Philippines, the regulations that provide for the hiring of contract workers state that contingent faculty workers do not receive coverage by civil service laws and rules. Therefore, they do not have the right to tenure and they do not receive credit for government service for time spent in contract faculty positions. This also means that they do not enjoy the benefits provided to other government employees according to Civil Service Commission (CSC)-Department of Budget and Managements (DBM)-Commission on Audit (COA) Joint Memo of 2017 [7]. Additionally, Memorandum Circular No. 20 of Civil Service Commission [8] also ruled out the possibility of tenure for contract faculty members and it stated that colleges and universities can separate contingent employees from service, with or without cause. If terminated, faculty members have no recourse to claim illegal termination and they have no entitlements to back wages or salaries, or to require reinstatement to their positions. Regardless of their part-time employment limitations, some contingent faculty members remain in their jobs for five or more years [9].

Stakeholders associated with colleges and universities typically seek to develop and maintain high levels of organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) among employees [10]. Some scholars have suggested that less than equitable salaries and working conditions can result in relatively lower levels of overall organizational commitment for affected employees [6] and comparatively, contingent faculty members fall into these categories. A growing number of studies have reported negative aspects of contingent faculty's lives such as depression, anxiety, and stress at work due to their contingent employment status, on the other hand, another line of research suggested that the influences of contingent faculty were not always negative [2].

Contrary to those potential expectations, literature shows that non-permanent faculty members generally reported having higher levels of well-being, general health, organizational citizenship, and task behavior than their counterparts in permanent positions [11]. These facts have been surprising as traditionally, we expect disadvantageous working condition to result to negative behavioral outcomes. Additionally, in as much as contingent employees may commit to organizations for various reasons, it also remains unclear how their organizational commitment impacts their citizenship behaviors and how their perceptions of organizational support might mediate those relationships. Magdalena [12] suggested mediation and moderation relations set between organizational commitment and the dimensions of OCB should be identified.

The purpose of this quantitative study included testing a theory of descriptive, predictive, and intervening organizational behavior relationships with contingent teachers in the public higher education sector in the Philippines. Specifically, it investigated the mediating relationship of perceived organizational support (POS) on the predictive relationships between affective, continuance, and normative organizational commitment (NOC) and OCB, as shown in the conceptual framework in Figure 1. The researchers also did this to: i) to determine which type of commitment leads to the highest collective level of OCB; and ii) to determine how the support (or lack thereof) that contingent faculty members perceive that they receive from their organizations might replace the need for or work with commitment to impact their OCB.

In the previous framework, the lines and figures represent theoretical relationships, based on past proven interactions within other studies. Dash dotted line represents the mediating relationship that resulted in intervening outcomes. Affective organizational commitment generally represents the motivation of want or desire of members to remain affiliated with their given organizations. It relates to organizational experiences and characteristics that make members feel "psychologically comfortable" (e.g., approachable managers and equitable treatment of employees) and that enhance feelings of self-efficacy. Continuance organizational commitment generally represents the motivation of having to stay, based on investments made in the organization or the lack of comparable membership alternatives while NOC represents the motivation of felt moral obligation to stay (e.g., having family members or friends instrumental in securing the given membership or position, having received prior economic or social assistance from the organization). The researchers have done away with identifying further antecedents of their organizational commitment as these are reflected also in the three constructs.

The specific objectives of the study included: i) Determining the levels of affective, continuance, and NOC; OCB; and POS for contingent faculty members who work in public universities in the Philippines; ii) Analyzing and reporting the results of the relationships between those variables; and iii) Identifying implications, drawing conclusions, and making recommendations based on the results.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study

2. RELATED LITERATURE

2.1. Organizational commitment

According to Allen and Meyer [13], posited that three types of organizational commitment exist, including affective, continuance, and normative. The affective component refers to the employee's emotional attachment to, identification with, and involvement to the organization [14], such as being at one with its core values and function. The continuance commitment refers to an employee's assumed cost of leaving the organization, such as the discomfort of having to find another job. Normative commitment on the other hand refers to the employee's feelings of obligation to remain in the organization because of some personal reasons like a responsibility to stay. Employees with strong affective commitment remain in the organization because they wanted to stay, those with strong continuance commitment stay because they need to, and those with strong normative commitment because they feel that they are obliged to [13].

Researchers in Scandinavia have shown that in temporary organizations, work autonomy, job complexity, and training all contribute to the overall commitment of employees [15]. Further, Chambel *et al.* [16] find out that temporary firm workers tend to develop a psychological contract with less emphasis on socio-emotional components than on economic ones. Researchers have previously proven that relationships exist between affective, continuance, and normative commitment, POS, and OCB. Other researchers such as Cordeiro, Cunha, and Laurencio [17] find out that affective and NOC results in higher level of altruism, conscientiousness, and civic virtue contrary to continuance commitment. Research by Nadim *et al.* [18] finds out the existence of relationship between the three types of organizational commitment and POS, among teachers in private sector universities in Pakistan.

2.2. Perceived organizational support

In previous research, Eisenberger *et al.* [19] suggested that POS serves as the input to social exchange theory that organizations provide, in order to receive organizational commitment from their associated members. In their theory, they also suggested that employees (members) develop beliefs and associated perceptions regarding how personified organizations provide for their social and material needs. Rhoades and Eisenberger [20] reviewed of over 70 studies suggests that basic antecedents of POS include fair organizational procedures, supervisor support, and favorable rewards and job conditions and that consequences include increased affective commitment to the organization, increased performance, and reduced withdrawal behaviors. For example, organizational support could include praise or approval for jobs well done, as well as pay, rank, job enrichment, and influence over organizational policies. In theory, the better the levels of treatment those members receive, the more highly members would think of the motives of their personified organizations and the more they would emotionally bond with those organizations. Researchers have found that employees display higher levels of POS when they believe that the associated

support results from the voluntary actions of their organizations, rather than from external constraints [13]. POS was found to be positively associated with job embeddedness and employees' positive evaluations on the extent of the organizational support they receive constitute a force encouraging them to stay with the organization [21].

2.3. Organizational citizenship behavior

Organizational citizenship represents behaviors that go beyond the "call of duty" or what West [22] otherwise described as discretionary effort, beyond the minimum acceptable standard. OCB serves as an important behavior for organizational functioning [18]. According to Lee and Allen [23] OCB includes behaviors such as cooperation with peers and co-workers, performing additional tasks without complaining, volunteering to help others in their tasks, using time and resources of the company efficiently, sharing ideas that can help improve the result of work and positively representing the organization. It consists of two dimensions, one, directed toward the organization and the other, directed toward individuals, especially other members (e.g., co-workers, superiors, and peers) [23]. Podsakoff *et al.* [24] provided four large categories of antecedents of OCB which are individual characteristics, task characteristics, organizational characteristics; and leadership behaviors.

The theoretical framework of this study is based on social exchange theory. Based on this theory, it is proposed that the obligation to exchange favorable treatment with favorable return behavior will enhance organizational commitment [19], [25]. For example, when organizations demonstrate that they value members, not only through pay and promotion, but also through demonstrations of approval and respect, it will enhance the feelings of well-being and morale of members [26]. In turn, this will further contribute to the positive behavior and positive performance of members and also to their affective feelings toward their associated organizations. These feelings will then develop into related levels of organizational commitment [27]. As such, it is specifically proposed that contingent faculty member employees, in public higher educational institutions in the Philippines develop and maintain affective, continuance, and NOC from their perceptions of having received organizational support through the treatment that they have experienced from their respective organizations [13], [19]. It is proposed that the three components of organizational commitment positively impact OCB in a linear manner and that perceived support from the organization positively contribute to OCB, thereby mediating the effects of all forms of organizational commitment. According to Zhang *et al.* [28], the theoretical foundations for responsible OCB based on reciprocity are social exchange theory and the obligation to reciprocate transforms it from discretionary behavior to required behavior. OCB would be engaging in assistance and cooperation beyond the role requirements [29].

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This study adopted a positivist view and used a cross-sectional research design to analyze the relationships between behavioral contexts that reflects the organizational commitment, POS, and OCB. The target population for this study included contingent teachers in either temporary, contractual, or part time employment arrangements with state universities and colleges in the Philippines. The study used the following criteria to make the participant selections: i) Currently employed as a contingent faculty member; ii) Not employed in a permanent position with any other universities or institutions of higher education; and iii) Not a retiree who returned to work in a contingent faculty position.

To determine the minimum sample size, the G*Power calculator was used, setting the parameters at: effect size $f^2=.35$, α error probability=.05, power=.90, and the total number of predictors=4. The associated calculation yielded a required minimum sample size of 50 participants. The researchers identified and included 92 contingent faculty members from four state universities and colleges in the Philippines.

Previously validated, standardized questionnaires were adopted and modified into a single survey using a five-point Likert-type scale to collect data in response to the items therein. To measure organizational commitment, it used an instrument by Allen and Meyer [13] which has coefficient alpha values of .87 for affective commitment; .79 for normative commitment; and .75 for continuance commitment. To measure POS, it used the instrument by Eisenberger *et al.* [19] which has previous coefficient alpha values of .97. To measure OCB, we used the instrument validated by Lee and Allen [23] which has a previous coefficient alpha values which ranged between .83 and .88.

Permission to use the mentioned instruments were obtained from the authors prior its utilization. The modified questionnaire was subjected to face and content validity test with expert validators who provided expert opinions and suggestions as to the content and quality of questions in the questionnaire vis-à-vis the research objectives. The instrument was piloted to 30 non-target respondents and internal reliability was checked for each variable and resulted to (Cronbach's alpha) .7-.75 for all organizational commitment constructs (affective, continuance, and normative), .80 for POS, and .83 for OCB.

To collect the data, the researcher gained permission to collect data from the presidents of four state universities and colleges and personally coordinated with its respective human resource management officer to assist with data gathering activities. The retrieved completed questionnaires were reviewed for completeness and consistency. It was then coded the data and subjected the data to analyses using SPSS version 23. Frequencies of the categorical demographics and the descriptives for the continuous variables were checked. Confirmatory factor analysis for internal consistency renders Cronbach's alpha scores of .74 for affective commitment, .60 for normative commitment, .72 for continuance commitment, .60 for POS and .80 for OCB. After completing descriptive analyses, researchers conducted test of relationship, using three predictor variables, the potential mediating variable, and the outcome variable. Next, the researchers then performed simple regressions to determine how each type of organizational commitment impacts OCB and completed the analyses, using Baron and Kenny procedure to check how POS might mediate those primary relationships [30].

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 92 respondents participated in the study. These consisted of 47 men and 45 women. The largest number of respondents had bachelor degrees, while the fewest number had doctor degrees, as noted in Figure 2. The respondents ranged in age from 16 to 47 years, with an average mean of 29.6 years. They ranged in tenure from having worked 1 to 10 semesters, with an average median of 3 semesters.

Figure 2. Participants' educational attainment

Internal consistency reliability appeared in the acceptable range for affective and continuance organizational commitment and for OCB. However, it was observed Cronbach's alpha scores of less than .7 for both NOC and POS. In fact, NOC displayed a value of <.50 when we included all 8 items. Therefore, item 1 of the scale measuring NOC was removed, in order to raise its Cronbach's alpha value to .60, as seen in Table 1. This table also shows the mean averages and standard deviations for these variables, with the mean OCB ranking higher than any of the predictor variables.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics for the focal variables

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Alpha
AOC	3.60	.52	.74
NOC	3.30	.48	.60
COC	3.03	.53	.72
POS	2.98	.42	.60
OCB	3.86	.40	.80

Pearson's correlation revealed the existence of relationships between both affective organizational commitment and NOC and OCB. Table 2 also shows that a relationship exists between POS and OCB. The results confirmed that of Huang and You [31] that components of organizational commitment have a considerably important influence on OCB. However, no relationship exists between any of the types of organizational commitment and POS.

Table 2. Correlations between OC, POS and OCB

		AOC	NOC	COC	POS
NOC	Pearson's r	.239*			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.022			
COC	Pearson's r	.132	.292**		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.208	.005		
POS	Pearson's r	.092	.090	-.028	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.383	.391	.788	
OCB	Pearson's r	.315*	.281**	.196	.252*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.007	.061	.015

The regression analyses as presented in Table 3 indicated that affective organizational commitment impacts OCB, displaying a fit model, $F(1,90)=9.93$, $p=.002<.05$, in which it accounts for 9% of the variance. The analyses also indicated that NOC impacts OCB, displaying a fit model, $F(1,90)=7.73$, $p=.007<.05$, in which it accounts for 7% of the variance and supports. Continuance organizational commitment failed to display a fit model, $F(1,90)=3.60$, $p=.061>.05$. Combining the predictors and using enter method demonstrated that organizational commitment collectively accounts for 12.6% of the associated variance. Regarding mediation, POS failed to display appropriate relationships with any of the factors representing organizational commitment, the first step required by the Baron and Kenny procedure [30].

Table 3. Summary of simple regressions of OC and OCB (N=92)

Variable	B	SE B	β	t	Sig.
AOC	.24	.08	.32	3.15	.002
NOC	.23	.08	.28	2.78	.007
COC	.15	.08	.20	1.90	.061

The main purpose of this present study included determining how the affective, normative, and continuance commitment impact the OCB of contingent teachers in select state universities and colleges in the Philippines and to determine the mediating effects of POS on those relationships. In this study, it was found that people in this category generally rate their OCB higher than their organizational commitment or any of the subcategories thereof. This likely contributed to the overall significant, but relatively low impact (12.6% of the variance) that organizational commitment has on OCB. These contingent teachers also rated OCB, along with all of the types of organizational commitment, higher than the perceived support that they receive from their given organizations.

The results were found antithetical to expectations, since: i) Arguably, out of all of the non-outcome variables considered herein, POS seems to most closely represent what organizations provide to members in social exchange theory and ii) The literature indicates that POS has served as a predictor of organizational commitment in several previous studies [32]. The fact that POS failed to correlate and subsequently regress on any of the subcategories of organizational commitment, which is differing to what other researchers such as that of Meyer, Morin, and Vandenberghe [33] also serves to further indicate that contingent faculty members develop and maintain commitment to their organizations from sources other than the perceived support that they receive from their organizations. Contingents teachers citizenship behavior develops its pedigree through time that they are in the organization [34] and not all forms of contingent employment are viewed by employees as and that not all forms of contingent employment contracts are viewed by workers as lesser to permanent jobs [35]. This confirms the findings of Lam, Hui, and Law [36] that there are performance norms that may transcend cultural values as well as performance norms that are affected by particular cultural values that affects OCB.

5. CONCLUSION

The study showed that contingent faculty members in public institutions of higher education in the Philippines, who develop and maintain affective and NOC, will display proportional levels of OCB. Therefore, with all other things equal, administrators in affected institutions should take required actions to increase these types of commitment in contingent faculty members, apart from providing for POS. Therefore, if these findings hold true among public institutions of higher education in the Philippines, to positively impact the subject levels of organizational commitment, administrators should: i) prefer hiring contingent faculty members who graduated from their institutions; ii) ensure that policies and procedures affecting contingent faculty members serve legitimate purposes and demonstrate comprehensive fairness and consistency, in both words and deeds; iii) provide regular training to enhance their capabilities; and iv) assign

to contingent faculty members the authority and accountability to complete work commensurate with their actual capabilities.

Several limitations emerged through the course of this study. Even though POS correlated with OCB, it did not correlate with (or regress on) affective, normative, or continuance organizational commitment. This suggests that other intervening variables confounded what has previously proven a reliable factor in explaining one aspect of social exchange theory. Without knowing what factors mediated the relationships between POS and organizational commitment, it has proven impossible to determine why this factor did not mediate the relationships between organizational commitment and OCB in the contexts that we investigated.

The relatively low impact of commitment on OCB indicates that other factors either directly impact OCB or they served in a mediating or moderating role between organizational commitment and OCB. Without further research, it will prove difficult to know which factors account for the other 87% of the variance in these specific contexts. In the future, researchers should determine which factors apply. They should also determine if the limitations observed in this present study extend to other populations within the contingent worker, higher education, and Filipino contexts.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Batiste, "Understanding contingent faculty: a quantitative study of engagement, satisfaction, commitment, and mentoring needs," Ph.D. dissertation, University of Nevada, Las Vegas, USA, 2016.
- [2] M. Y. Cha and C. Carrier, "Contingent faculty perceptions of organizational support, workplace attitudes, and teaching evaluations at a public research university," *Journal for the Study of Postsecondary and Tertiary Education*, vol. 1, pp. 121–151, 2016, doi: 10.28945/3429.
- [3] R. A. Clay, "Untenured and untethered: the trend of replacing tenure-track faculty with adjuncts means low pay, worse academic outcomes and more," *Monitor in Psychology*, vol. 47, no. 9, p. 54, 2016.
- [4] J. R. Frye, "Organizational pressures driving the growth of contingent faculty," *New Directions for Institutional Research*, vol. 2017, no. 176, pp. 27–39, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1002/ir.20242.
- [5] A. Drake, L. Struve, S. A. Meghani, and B. Bukoski, "Invisible labor, visible change: non-tenure-track faculty agency in a research university," *The Review of Higher Education*, vol. 42, no. 4, pp. 1635–1664, 2019, doi: 10.1353/rhe.2019.0078.
- [6] S. P. Robbins and T. A. Judge, *Organizational behavior*, 18th ed. Hoboken: Pearson Education Inc. Prentice Hall, 2019.
- [7] Republic of The Philippines, Civil Service Commission. *Joint Memorandum Circular NO. 1s. 2017: Rules and Regulations Governing Contract of Service and Job Order Workers in the Government*. Philippine Civil Service Commission, Department of Budget and Management 2017. [Online]. Available: [https://www.dbm.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/Issuances/2017/Joint%20Circular/CSC-COA-DBM%20JOINT%20CIRCULAR%20NO.%201%20\(1\).pdf](https://www.dbm.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/Issuances/2017/Joint%20Circular/CSC-COA-DBM%20JOINT%20CIRCULAR%20NO.%201%20(1).pdf).
- [8] Republic of The Philippines, Civil Service Commission (CSC), "CSC Memorandum Circulars 20, s. 2002: Revised Policies on Temporary Appointments and Publication of Vacant Positions," CIVIL SERVICE GUIDE: A Compilation of Issuances on Philippine Civil Service, 2002. [Online]. Available: <https://www.csguide.org/items/show/487>.
- [9] W. R. Adan, "TURNING POINT: job order: injustice and anomaly in government service," *Minda News*, Naawan, Misamis Oriental, Philippines, Jan. 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mindanews.com/mindaviews/2015/01/turning-point-job-order-injustice-and-anomaly-in-government-service/>
- [10] T. F. Thabo, N.-O. Esther, R. W. Debra, F. Ntonghanwah, and G. L. James, "Factors associated with organizational commitment of academic employees in Botswana," *International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 56–64, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.5897/IJEAPS2017.0563.
- [11] D. Guest and M. Clinton, "Temporary employment contracts, workers' well-being and behaviour: evidence from the UK (Department of Management Working Paper 38)," London: King's College London, 2006.
- [12] S. M. Magdalena, "The effects of organizational citizenship behavior in the academic environment," *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 127, pp. 738–742, Apr. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.03.346.
- [13] N. J. Allen and J. P. Meyer, "The measurement and antecedents of affective, continuance and normative commitment to the organization," *Journal of Occupational Psychology*, vol. 63, no. 1, pp. 1–18, Mar. 1990, doi: 10.1111/j.2044-8325.1990.tb00506.x.
- [14] U. Colakoglu, U. Culha, and H. Atay, "The effects of perceived organisational support on employees' affective outcomes: evidence from the hotel industry," *Tourism and Hospitality Management*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 125–150, 2010, doi: 10.20867/thm.16.2.1.
- [15] T. Spanuth and A. Wald, "Understanding the antecedents of organizational commitment in the context of temporary organizations: an empirical study," *Scandinavian Journal of Management*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 129–138, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.scaman.2017.06.002.
- [16] M. J. Chambel, L. Lorente, V. Carvalho, and I. M. Martinez, "Psychological contract profiles among permanent and temporary agency workers," *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 79–94, Feb. 2016, doi: 10.1108/JMP-02-2014-0070.
- [17] J. Cordeiro, P. Cunha, and A. Laurencio, "Conflict management, commitment and organizational citizenship behaviors: empirical study in higher education institution," in *III International Forum on Management: Value Creation and Local Heritage*, 2019, doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16475.21280.
- [18] M. Nadim, M. M. Hassan, S. Abbas, and A. Naveed, "The role of organizational commitment and perceived organizational support in promoting organizational citizenship behavior," *PEOPLE: International Journal of Social Sciences*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 54–67, Nov. 2016, doi: 10.20319/pijss.2016.23.5467.
- [19] R. Eisenberger, R. Huntington, S. Hutchison, and D. Sowa, "Perceived organizational support," *Journal of Applied Psychology*, vol. 71, no. 3, pp. 500–507, Aug. 1986, doi: 10.1037/0021-9010.71.3.500.
- [20] L. Rhoades and R. Eisenberger, "Perceived organizational support: a review of the literature," *Journal of Applied Psychology*, vol. 87, no. 4, pp. 698–714, 2002, doi: 10.1037/0021-9010.87.4.698.

- [21] A. H. Dirican and O. Erdil, "Linking abusive supervision to job embeddedness: the mediating role of perceived organizational support," *Current Psychology*, vol. 41, no. 2, pp. 990–1005, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s12144-020-00716-1.
- [22] G. R. B. West, "An alternative method to investigate organizational effectiveness: an adaptation and expansion of Robert Terry's model," *Emerging Leadership Journeys*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 62–75, 2008.
- [23] K. Lee and N. J. Allen, "Organizational citizenship behavior and workplace deviance: the role of affect and cognitions," *Journal of Applied Psychology*, vol. 87, no. 1, pp. 131–142, 2002, doi: 10.1037/0021-9010.87.1.131.
- [24] P. M. Podsakoff, S. B. MacKenzie, J. B. Paine, and D. G. Bachrach, "Organizational citizenship behaviors: a critical review of the theoretical and empirical literature and suggestions for future research," *Journal of Management*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 513–563, 2000, doi: doi.org/10.1177/014920630002600307.
- [25] S. Rashid, G. Dastgeer, and T. Kayani, "A social exchange perspective through the lens of an individual: relationship between LMX, voice and organizational commitment in academia," *Business & Economic Review*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 41–64, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.22547/BER/10.3.3.
- [26] S. Chelliah, N. Sundarapandiyam, and B. Vinoth, "A research on employees' organisational commitment in organisations: a case of SMEs in Malaysia," *International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research (IJMSR)*, vol. 3, no. 7, pp. 10–18, 2015.
- [27] R. Cropanzano, E. L. Anthony, S. R. Daniels, and A. V. Hall, "Social exchange theory: a critical review with theoretical remedies," *Academy of Management Annals*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 479–516, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.5465/annals.2015.0099.
- [28] Y. Zhang, J. Liao, and J. Zhao, "Research on the organizational citizenship behavior continuum and its consequences," *Frontiers of Business Research in China*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 364–379, Sep. 2011, doi: 10.1007/s11782-011-0135-2.
- [29] A. S. Boyce, A. M. Ryan, A. L. Imus, and F. P. Morgeson, "Temporary worker, permanent loser? A model of the stigmatization of temporary workers," *Journal of Management*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 5–29, 2007, doi: 10.1177/0149206306296575.
- [30] R. M. Baron and D. A. Kenny, "The moderator–mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations," *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, vol. 51, no. 6, pp. 1173–1182, 1986, doi: 10.1037/0022-3514.51.6.1173.
- [31] C.-C. Huang and C.-S. You, "The three components of organizational commitment on in-role behaviors and organizational citizenship behaviors," *African Journal of Business Management*, vol. 5, no. 28, pp. 11335–11344, Nov. 2011, doi: 10.5897/AJBM10.1623.
- [32] E. Ahmed, B. D'Netto, J. Chelliah, and E. Fein, "Psychological contract breach: consequences of unkept promises of permanent employment," *Contemporary Management Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 183–212, Jun. 2016, doi: 10.7903/cmr.13914.
- [33] J. P. Meyer, A. J. S. Morin, and C. Vandenberghe, "Dual commitment to organization and supervisor: a person-centered approach," *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, vol. 88, pp. 56–72, Jun. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.jvb.2015.02.001.
- [34] Z. U. Bukhari, "Key antecedents of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) in the banking sector of Pakistan," *International Journal of Business and Management*, vol. 3, no. 12, pp. 106–115, Feb. 2009, doi: 10.5539/ijbm.v3n12p106.
- [35] H. Buddelmeyer, D. Mvcar, and M. Wooden, "Non-standard "contingent" employment and job satisfaction: a panel data analysis," *Industrial Relations*, vol. 54, no. 2, pp. 256–275, 2015, doi: 10.1111/irel.12090.
- [36] S. S. K. Lam, C. Hui, and K. S. Law, "Organizational citizenship behavior: comparing perspectives of supervisors and subordinates across four international samples," *Journal of Applied Psychology*, vol. 84, no. 4, pp. 594–601, Aug. 1999, doi: 10.1037/0021-9010.84.4.594.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Eva Joy C. Palma is a faculty member at Northern Iloilo State University Barotac Viejo Campus, Barotac Viejo, Iloilo, Philippines. She is a holder of Doctor of Management (major in public management) degree and a Licensed Professional Teacher in Social Science. She is teaching social science courses and works with the Office of Extension and Community Involvement Services and Office of Scientific Publication. Her researches focused on public administration, organizational behavior, gender and development, culture, and organizational leadership and social sciences. She can be contacted at email: yojava_19@yahoo.com.ph.

George R. West is an adjunct professor at Central Philippine University, Jaro, Iloilo City, Philippines. At Central Philippine University, he is teaching in the MA, MBA, MS, and Doctor of Management programs and worked with the Director of Institutional Research and Vice President of Academic Affairs, in the fields of project development and management. He was also a faculty at Regent University, Virginia Beach, VA, United States. He can be contacted at email: dr.budwest@cpu.edu.ph or geowest.phd@gmail.com.